

“Human Resource Development practices in Private and Cooperative Sector milk processing organizations in western Maharashtra: A comparative study”

Prof Sambhaji V. Mane

*School of Management Sciences, Swami Ramanand Teerth Marathwada University Nanded's Sub Campus Peth, AUSA road, Latur Maharashtra, India - 413531

Abstract- HRD practices in Private and Cooperative Sector milk processing organizations in Western Maharashtra were found below the standard at fair and poor level; did not serve any of its meaningful purpose and strongly need to be restored and utilize to get best HRD practices result in both the sectors in order to sustain in severe global competition.

Key words:

HRD, Policy, HRD practices, Private, Cooperative, Milk organizations, Nashik, Comparism

Introduction

The economic performance of U.K. in varied areas was damaging than two of its major competitors' – France and West Germany due to lack of attention on training (Labour Research - 1988). Human Resources are the greatest of all our assets (Shah 1990). Organizations or even country cannot deny its importance; hence, developed human resource act as important resource to the organization to increase effectiveness and play vital role in coping with change and innovations (*Ravishanker and Mishra 1988*). Companies all over the world recognizing training and development of human resource, as it is the single major contributor to corporate growth, innovation, dynamism and prosperity (*Sondni 1992*). Role of HRD in the new economic environment is, thus, becoming important in improving technical, managerial skills and employee motivation to face today's challenges of liberalization (*T V Rao and others 1994*). The degree of survivability of the organization increases with the increase in quality of and dynamism of the workforce. In today's business, the only viable strategy is to recruit good people, develop them and retain as many stars as possible (*Groysberg, Nanda and Noharia 2004*). Every organization should create an inspiring environment that would motivate workforce to perform better and boost efficiency (*Sawant 2004*). Economic liberalization and WTO agreement energize foreign companies to rush to India and exploit the amply available raw milk resources. The MNC'S in India have focused on their milk processing plant in India. Hence, it is a high time for Indian organizations to carryout business practices on scientific line in both the private and cooperative sectors milk processing organizations in Western Maharashtra.

Methodology

In Pune and Nashik region of Western Maharashtra, among the registered organizations, 111 Private and Cooperative sector milk-processing organizations were actually functioning. Out of these, 16 organizations were incorporated in the sample of the present study - 8 from private and 8 from co-operative sector - by adopting following criteria as: equal number of organizations from both the region, only one organization from the district, well reputed organization, permission for research, organization with 5 years of registration, more than 30 employees, daily milk collection minimum of 5,000 lit. and plant handling capacity minimum of 20,000 lit/day. The total number of workforce in these organizations was 6047; out of these 836 belonged to management staff and 5211 belonged to employee's category. As it was quite difficult to conduct the survey for all the workforce, 30% of both the category (1814) i.e. 251 management respondents and 1563 employee respondents were selected for the present study

by adopting proportionate convenience sampling technique to accomplish the objectives of the study:

1. To examine HRD practices being followed in selected milk processing organizations and
2. To suggest remedial measures for to enhance effectiveness of HRD practices.

Researcher collected primary data through survey method, discussions and interviews, non-participatory observation method and secondary data through documentary research method and unstructured interviews.

The geographical scope of the study covers the entire division of Western Maharashtra, the topical scope covers the evaluation of the on-going HRD practices, the analytical scope covers the fulfillment of the set objectives and the functional scope is confined to offering meaningful recommendations for improving the HRD practices of the organizations. However, the interview schedules used for collecting the primary data were neither designed to ascertain the respondents' biases nor to gauge the influence of these biases on the intensity of their responses. Again, the study has included urban and rural areas of Pune and Nashik region the spatio-temporal perceptions of individual employee's differ widely and have accordingly influences their responses.

Results and Discussions

The management respondents' interviewed was male, mostly 26-55 years old, with an average service of 6-30 years. They had mostly joined supervisor/officer level in their 20 to 25 years of age after completion of diploma/graduation and neither of them were members of employee association. The employee respondents are 18-45 years old, below H.S.C. qualified males with a veteran of average 20 years. They have invariably joined milk-processing organizations, as a worker and neither of them were members of employee association. The average personal profile of the respondents is presented in Table 1.1

Table 1.1- Average personal profile of the respondents:

Sr. No.	Respondents	Sex	Age Group	Service in years	Educational level	Employee Asso. Membership
1	Management	Male	25-55	6 to 30	Diploma(IDD),UG, PG	No
2	Employee	Male	18-45	0 to 20	Up to HSC	No

The opinion of both the respondents' group regarding existing HRD practices in milk processing organizations of private and co-operative sector in Western Maharashtra were collected through "Five – Point Likert Scale with No Opinion" and interprets the data as given in Table No.1.2

Table 1.2- Process of data interpretation of the HRD Practices

1. Separate Human Resource Management department manage employees activities. <u>Level of Agreement:</u> 1: Strongly Disagree, 2: Disagree, 3: Partly Disagree Partly Agree 4: Agree, 5: Strongly Agree, 0: No Opinion.	1	2	3	4	5	0 -- Scale
	x 43	x 34	x 2	x 96	x 97	x 2 = 274 Respondents
$43 + 68 + 6 + 384 + 485 + 0 = 986$ Total Score $= 986$ Total Score / 274 Respondents = 3.59 Mean Score Highest possible Mean Score is 5.00 = 100 % Hence 3.59 = 71.80 %						

Mean scores above '4.5' (90.00%) indicate the respondents 'outstanding' rating of the HRD aspect; score between '4.5' and '4' (90.00-- 80.00%) indicate an 'excellent' opinion;

'4' and '3.5' (80.00--70.00%) 'good'; '3.5' and '3' (70.00-- 60.00%) 'fair' opinion, implying that the particular HRD aspect may be improved through suitable methods and effort and between '3' and '2.5' (60.00-- 50.00%) 'poor' and 'Below 2.5' (Below 50.00%) 'very poor' opinion, indicating the need for a drastic intervention to bring about a change for the better.

The HRD practices opinion survey data of Management and Employee respondents of Private, and Cooperative sector of Western Maharashtra interpreted in above manner and presented in Table No.1.3. The derived mean score of private and co-operative sector HRD practice were used for plotting the line graph and to compare the effectiveness of each HRD practices in both the sectors with respect to standard score and to comment on it with respect actual existence in both the sector. Graphically it is presented in Graph No 1.1

Table 1.3- HRD Practices Opinion Survey of Management and Employee Respondents from Private, and Cooperative Sector of Western Maharashtra:

HRD Practices	Private Sector			Cooperative Sector		
	Mgt. Resp. (49)	Emp. Resp. (225)	Mean Score	Mgt. Resp (202)	Emp. Resp (1338)	Mean Score
1.HRD Concept	2.5986	2.9504	2.775	2.816	2.7993	2.808
2.Role Analysis	2.9388	2.9822	2.961	2.901	2.9036	2.902
3.Human ResourcePlanning	3.4082	3.6622	3.535	3.201	3.2216	3.212
4.Recruitment	3.3844	3.6541	3.519	2.655	2.821	2.739
5.Selection	2.69	2.46	2.575	2.684	2.729	2.707
6.Placement	2.8061	3.5644	3.185	3.138	3.346	3.242
7. Induction orOrientation	3.0153	3.7278	3.372	2.534	2.7435	2.639
8.Performance Appraisal	2.9014	3.2348	3.068	2.271	2.433	2.352
9.Career Planningand Development	2.7015	2.3853	2.543	2.204	2.3338	2.269
10. Training	2.7429	2.8182	2.781	2.219	2.3349	2.277
11. Development	3.2694	3.1111	3.19	2.811	2.9315	2.872
12.Organisation Development & change	3.4558	3.3074	3.382	3.047	3.1134	3.081
13. Workersparticipation in Mgmt.	3.1755	2.7742	2.975	2.662	2.845	2.754
14. Quality ofWork life	3.3333	3.517	3.425	3.305	3.4641	3.385
15. QualityCircle	1.5714	1.3015	1.436	2.673	2.8784	2.776
16. EmployeeCounseling	3.6327	3.8444	3.739	3.059	3.5135	3.286
17.Team Management	3.1837	3.603	3.393	3.306	3.4063	3.357
18. Job Evaluation	2.4857	3.3289	2.907	2.350	2.3857	2.368
19. Wages andSalary Admn.	3.256	3.7107	3.483	2.946	3.0445	2.995
20.Employee Benefits	3.0612	3.5192	3.29	3.459	3.701	3.58
21. Rewards	2.7619	3.283	3.022	3.501	3.5912	3.546
22.Grievance Procedure	2.8027	3.203	3.003	3.151	3.2434	3.198

Graph No1.1: Comparism of HRD Practices in Private and Cooperative Sector milk processing

organizations in Western Maharashtra -

Conclusions & Recommendations:

On the basis of data presentation, analysis and interpretation and comparison of HRD Practices Opinion Survey of Management and Employee Respondents from Private and Cooperative Sector milk processing in Western Maharashtra indicates that majority of the HRD practices in both the sectors were found fair, poor and very poor and neither of them ‘outstanding’ and ‘excellent’ category. It implied HRD aspect need to be improved through suitable methods and effort and also implies the need for a drastic intervention to bring about a change for the better practices in both the region.

Accordingly, recommendation made for effective development of HRD practices in Private and Cooperative Sector, as:

1. Organizations need to be sensitive towards HRD practices
2. Separate full time HRD Manager preferably MBA HR need to be appointed
3. Management need to give strong support to all the HRD activities being implemented
4. Focus on each HRD activities implementation and evaluation
5. Find out the structural loopholes in the organization, if any
6. Create favorable organization culture.
7. Establish policies in the organization.

8. Publicize the HRD activity widely in the organization.
9. Establish committees, involve employees in the activities
10. Continuous training, counseling and guidance need to be available to the workforce
11. Follow-up and implement the HRD activity.

Overall, HRD practices in private and cooperate sector milk processing organizations in Western Maharashtra were judged on the basis of theoretical presentation and the analysis of the empirical data. Accordingly, it is concluded that in private and cooperative sector milk processing organizations in Western Maharashtra, HRD practices were poor and need to be improved in order to sustain in global competition.

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